

Effect of Incorporating Additional Thermoplastic into Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Composites Prepared by Electrodeposition Resin Molding Method

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Background and Objective

- Thermoplastic polymer composite has exceptional combination of mechanical performance, design flexibility, and recyclability.
- Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) has widespread application in aircraft

Fig. 1. Application of CFRTP in aircraft [1]

Subject

Electrodeposition resin molding method (EDRM) only works on thermoset (epoxy) polymer.

Preparing Nylon 6 based carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite

Objective

To check the compatibility of nylon 6 and epoxy into carbon fiber/nylon 6/epoxy and check its effect on the composite properties

Fig. 2. Reaction between nylon 6 and epoxy [2]

What is EDRM?

- EDRM – Electrodeposition Resin Molding Method
- Coating technology for automobile bodies had been adopted

Fig. 3. Graphical representation and actual setup of EDRM

Fig. 4. Mechanism of EDRM [3]

Advantages of EDRM

- Less void
- Easy handling
- Uniform mixture of fiber and matrix
- Autoclave not required
- No need of vacuum bag or moulding

Fig. 5. Relationship of voltage/current with time

Experimental Procedure

Stacking sequence

Table 1. Experimental condition

Sample	Stacking Sequence
1	No N6
2	1 Layer of N6
3	2 Layers of N6
4	3 Layers of N6 (Alternate)
5	3 Layers of N6 (Middle)

Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the Four-point bending test, Roughness test and Raman Spectroscopy are displayed below.

Fig. 6. Bending strength of carbon fiber/nylon 6/epoxy composites

Inserting nylon 6 sheet into CFRP can significantly increase the bending strength of CFRP, however, surprisingly adding one layer of nylon 6 has higher flexural strength than adding multiple layers

Fig. 7. Bending modulus of carbon fiber/nylon 6/epoxy composites

The same scenario was also observed in case of flexural modulus. The maximum bending modulus was achieved when 1 layer of nylon 6 was inserted into CFRP.

Fig. 8. Bending strength and modulus of carbon fiber/hot-pressed nylon 6/epoxy composites

The CFRP including the hot-pressed nylon 6 layer showed 59% increase in bending strength than the CFRP without any nylon 6 layer. Moreover, using the hot-pressed nylon 6 layer increased the bending strength by 6% of CFRP with nylon 6 layer that wasn't hot-pressed.

Fig. 9. Surface topography of carbon fiber/nylon 6/epoxy composites

Fig. 10. Raman spectroscopy of carbon fiber/nylon 6/epoxy composites

Fig. 11. SEM image of CFRP fabricated by EDRM

Conclusion

- The effect of adding Nylon 6 into CFRP were investigated
- Nylon 6 has a great compatibility with epoxy which results in higher bending strength and impact energy

Future Studies

- Effect of adding other thermoplastics other than nylon 6 with epoxy to check compatibility and made a comparative study

References

- Mrazova, M. (2013). Advanced composite materials of the future in aerospace industry. Incas bulletin, 5(3), 139.
- Gorton, B. S. (1964). Interaction of nylon polymers with epoxy resins in adhesive blends. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 8(3), 1287-1295.
- Islam, M. T., Honda, S., Katagiri, K., Sasaki, K., & Takeda, R. (2024). Investigation of manufacture variables on the mechanical properties of CFRP prepared by electrodeposition resin molding method. Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures, 31(29), 11363-11378.

